

On-Farm Evaluation and Demonstration of Integrated Wheat Rust Management in Central Ethiopia Region

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Abstract

Ethiopia has enormous potential to produce wheat (*Triticum spp*) in vast amount. However, the production is curtailed by various biotic and abiotic stresses, among these yellow rust diseases caused by *Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici* and stem rust caused by (*Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici*) are the most devastating wheat production bottleneck in Ethiopia. Thus, the current study was designed with the goal of demonstrating integrated wheat rust management in the Alichu and Mareko districts during the 2018 growing season. Farmers were chosen specifically based on the availability of suitable farm land and their willingness to participate in the demonstration fields. The experiment was conducted in a single plot design with farmers serving as replications. Two best performing moderately susceptible bread wheat varieties were used each at different location. Both fungicides showed significant differences in reducing rust severity. The maximum present diseases control 79.3% of yellow rust was recorded from Rex®Duo. In another location the highest stem rust disease control of 75.6% was recorded from Tilt 250 EC. Both fungicide applications showed a considerable production advantage over untreated plots. Rex®Duo controlled effectively the yellow rust and Tilt 250 EC control the stem rust and increasing yield of bread wheat. Therefore, based on cost benefit analysis, the combination use of Denda'a and Rex®Duo is the best integrated yellow rust management way, whereas the combination of Ogolcho and Tilt 250 EC proved the optimum grain yield by decreasing stem rusts and can be recommended for the area and similar agro-ecologies.

Keywords: *Fungicides, Severity, stem rust, Wheat, Yellow rust.*

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Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum spp.*) is one of the most important cereal crops produced worldwide (Curtis et al., 2002), and it is thought to be the first crop ever to be cultivated, contributing significantly to human economic and social development worldwide (Thabet and Najeeb, 2017). In the 2022-2023 growing season,

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approximately 781 million metric tons of wheat was produced worldwide (Statista, 2023). Bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of Ethiopia's major cereal crops, accounting for approximately 1.89 million hectares of arable land (13.4% of total cereal acreage) (CSA, 2022). World wheat production trend increasing for the past two decades (Sendhil et al., 2023). However, the production is threatened by wheat diseases and pests globally (Singh et al. 2016; Serfling et al. 2016, Oerke, 2006; Beddow). Among these diseases rust are the most distractive constraint in East Africa regions of Ethiopia and Kenya (FAO, 2024). Rusts, particularly stripe and stem rusts, are regarded as the most significant biotic constraints to sustainable wheat production in several countries, including Ethiopia. This is due to the ability of the pathogen to evolve rapidly into new races and to migrate long distances by air borne dispersal.

Yellow rust, caused by (*Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici*), is one of the most widespread and destructive diseases of wheat worldwide (Chai et al., 2015). In severe cases, up to 100% yield loss was recorded due to yellow rust in highly susceptible varieties (CIMMYT, 2010). Stem rust, caused by (*Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici*), is the other most economical disease of wheat and a threat to global food security (Solh et al., 2012; Chaves et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2014; Gangwar et al., 2017; Schwessinger, 2017). The yield loss caused by stem rust is depend up on the resistance level of variety used, the crop growth stage and time of epidemic onset. During epidemics, stem rust can cause up to 100% yield loss in susceptible wheat varieties (Bechere et al., 2000).

There are different management approaches to minimize and overcome the loss caused by rust diseases: Planting resistance cultivars, planting several cultivars differing in genetic and agronomic characteristics, application of foliar fungicides, and cultural practices such as controlling volunteer wheat and avoiding excessive fertilization and irrigation (Ellis ET AL., 2014; Olesen et al, 2003. Host resistance is the chief line of long-term defiance mechanism against wheat rust diseases. Due to these growing resistant cultivars is the most efficient and environment friendly method to reduce yield losses caused by rust (Line and Chen, 1995; Zhang et al., 2017).Foliar fungicide applications have become an important component of wheat rust management. But, there is scare information regarding on the effects of fungicide applications on yield response of wheat by growers in an area. Now a day it's not possible to get profitable yield from wheat without supplement of fungicides application (Wanyera et al., 2009).This is because; most of the commercial wheat varieties doesn't withstanding the effect of rusts. Thus, to solve such problems, it's evident that demonstration of integrated diseases management methods has a significant role using best performing wheat varieties and fungicide to minimize the yield loss caused by rust disease.

Material and Methods

Descriptions of the Study Site

The present research was conducted in the research sub site of Mareko and Alichu during the 2018 growing season. Mareko is found in the Gurage zone, situated under midland agro-ecologies. Geographically, Mareko is located at 08°05'67"N, 38°18'18"E and 1824 m.a.s.l. The mean annual rainfall in the area is 675 mm, while the mean average air temperature is 27.5 °C. The soil type is dominated by clay soil (Cromic Luvisole and Haplic phaeozems). The location is hot spot for stem rust infestation. Alichu research site is located at 07°56'96"N, 38°09'39"E and 2870 m.a.s.l. The annual rainfall ranges between 750 and 1190 mm, indicating highland agro ecology. The average annual minimum and maximum temperatures are 8.1°C and 16.7°C, respectively. The most common soil type is clay (pellic vertisole). The locations represent yellow rust prone areas of central Ethiopia region and both locations characterized by bimodal rainfall, the short rainy season extending from March to May and the main rainy season from June to September.

Experimental Design and Treatments

A single plot design was used to demonstrate the effect of fungicides against wheat rust disease. Two moderately susceptible bread wheat varieties namely, Denda'a for yellow rust and Ogolcho for stem rust were used in the demonstration. The two fungicide types with different mode of action used for the experiment were Rex® Duo and Tilt® 250E.C at a rate of 0.5l/ha⁻¹ are applied for both yellow rust and stem rust disease. Unsprayed plot was included as control for comparison. A seed of the wheat was sown by hand drilling at the recommended rate of 125kg/ha⁻¹. Both diseases were allowed to develop naturally in each variety without any artificial inoculation. Fungicides were sprayed at the initial rust symptom using manual Knapsack sprayer in 250lha⁻¹ of water when disease severity reached 20% on spreader rows. Each fungicide was applied two times based on company recommendation rate. During fungicide sprays, plastic sheets were used to protect the adjacent plots from fungicide drifts. Plot size was 10 x 10m or 100m² for each treatment. The distance between plots was 1m and twenty five 25 row plot of 0.2m spacing were used. Experimental plots were fertilized with NPS fertilizer at the rate of 100kg/ha⁻¹ just at planting and Urea (41kgN/46kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹) with split application. Weeding and other cultural practices were carried out according to the recommendation of areas.

Data Collected

Plot-based data were collected from 21 central rows (92m² net areas) per plot. Individual plant-based data was collected from ten randomly selected and pre-tagged plants prior to the appearance of disease symptoms and the mean of ten plants was used for data analysis. The data was collected using the parameters described below.

Diseases Assessment

Yellow rust and stem rust severity was recorded four times at 10 days interval starting from appearance of the disease symptom to physiological maturity of the crop based on the modified Cobb's scale (Peterson et al., 1948). Rust severity was scored prior to each spray of fungicide and terminal severity was used for data analysis. Disease parameters were calculated using the formula described below.

Disease Severity

$$\text{Disease severity} = \left(\frac{\text{Area of plant tissue affected}}{\text{Total area of plant tissue examined}} \right) * 100 \quad (1)$$

Present Disease Control

$$\text{PDC} = \left(\frac{\text{Percent Severity in treated plot} - \text{percent severity in untreated plot}}{\text{percent severity in untreated plot}} \right) * 100 \quad (2)$$

Yellow rust head infection (HI)

Yellow rust head infection (HI) = the numbers of infected spikelet on individual head were counted from 10 randomly selected plants and the average of 10 plants was used for data analysis.

$$\text{HI} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of infected spikelet}}{\text{Total number of spikelet examined on the head}} \right) * 100 \quad (3)$$

Yield parameter assessment

All agronomic data were recorded from 21 central rows on each experimental unit. Details of the agronomic parameters measured are the following.

Kernels per spike (KPS): The numbers of kernels of main tillers on each of 10 randomly selected plants were counted and the average of 10 plants was used for data analysis.

Thousand kernels weight (TKW) (g): The weight of one thousand kernels was counted using a seed counter, adjusting to 12.5% moisture content and weighing them using sensitive balance.

Grain yield (GY): Grain yield in g/plot at moisture content of 12.5% was recorded and converted in to kg/ha⁻¹.

Yield Loss Estimation

Yield loss estimation is mandatory to develop strategies for disease control particularly through breeding objectives for disease resistance (Simmonds, 1988). The relative losses in yield and yield component of each variety were determined as a percentage of that of the protected plots of the respective variety.

$$RL(\%) = \left(\frac{Y_1 - Y_2}{Y_1} \right) * 100 \quad (4)$$

Where, RL = relative loss (reduction of the parameters grain yield and TKW), Y₁ = mean of the respective parameter on protected plots (plots with maximum protection) and Y₂ = mean of the respective parameter in unprotected plots (i.e. unsprayed plots or sprayed plots with varying level of disease).

Cost Benefit Analysis

Fungicide and application costs were used to calculate net returns from applying fungicides to manage wheat rust. During study average wheat price was used from local market. Average fungicide prices (\$ ha⁻¹) were obtained by surveying local distributing agencies and three chemical companies (Makamba plc, General Chemical Trading Pvt. Co, and Makubu plc) and averaged (Table 1). Fungicide application costs were obtained by surveying of four large-scale farm applicators in an area. Net return from fungicide application was calculated as follows: $R_n = Y_i P - (F_c + A_c)$ Where, R_n is the net return from fungicide application (\$ ha⁻¹); Y_i is yield increase from fungicide application (kg ha⁻¹), obtained by subtracting the yield in the control treatment from the yield in the fungicide treatments; P is the wheat price (\$ kg⁻¹); F_c is the fungicide cost (\$ ha⁻¹) and A_c is the fungicide application cost (\$ ha⁻¹).

Table 1. The Fungicide Costs, Fungicide Application Cost, and Wheat Prices Used in Cost Benefit Analysis

Fungicides	Fungicides cost	Fungicide application	FC + AC	Wheat price
	FC (\$ha ⁻¹)	cost (AC) Cost (ha ⁻¹)	(\$ha ⁻¹)	(ha ⁻¹)
Rex@Duo	51	18.45	69.45	69.3
Tilt 250 EC	39.2	18.45	57.65	69.3

Source: Survey data on Makamba plc, General Chemical & Trading Pvt. Co, and Makubu plc.

Results and Discussion

Diseases Severity

The occurrence of yellow rust during 2018 was slightly severed and treatment combinations differed in terms of disease severity reduction. During the epidemic period the yellow rust severity was higher at Alichu. The maximum terminal yellow rust of 49.3% was recorded from untreated plot, whereas the lowest yellow rust severity of 10.2% was recorded after application of Rex®Duo (Table 2). On the other hand application of Tilt 250 EC reduced diseases severity by 17.8% (Table 2). Control treatment had a progressive increase in disease severity due to the absence of fungicide treatment. This could be due to favorable weather conditions and the evolvement of new pathotype in an area. Beest et al (2008) also reported that weather factors influence occurrence and severity of stripe rust epidemics on winter wheat. Foliar spray of Rex®Duo better reduced yellow rust severity in comparison with Tilt 250 EC. Furthermore, two times applications fungicide yielded a significantly higher return than a single application.

At Mareko the maximum terminal stem severity of 33.8% were recorded from untreated plots. (Table 3) However, after application of Tilt 250 EC the disease reduced to 7.1% (Table 3). On the other hand intermediate result of stem rust severity (12.6%) reduction was recorded after the application of Rex®Duo (Table 3). These result in a comparable reduction in stem rust pressure due to fungicide action. In spite of diseases control of Tilt 250 EC, frequent application result in relative resistance against stem rust pathogen. Similarly, (Hollomon, 2015) reported a recent increase in fungicide resistance among plant pathogenic fungi. Intense utilization of Tilt 250 EC fungicide in the past, prohibit the risk of resistance by the pathogen. Therefore, this research finding directing the adjustment active ingredients found in the chemical by producers and consultants to enhance their efficacy of fungicide. However, dependency on chemical utilization by itself not a sustainable strategy all time. As a result, focusing on varietal development is a long-term solution, as is incorporating strong resistant genes into wheat material to combat virulent pathogens.

Table 2. Effect of Fungicide on Yellow Rust and Yield Component of Wheat

Treatment		Yellow rust							
Variety	Fungicide	TRS (%)	PDC (%)	HI (%)	KPS	TKW (g)	GY(kgha-1)	GY (loss)	
								(kgha ⁻¹)	(%)
Denda'a	Rex®Duo	10.2	79.3	2.3	59.8	40.3	4737.2	0.00	0.00
	Tilt 250 EC	17.8	63.8	6.8	55.3	37.9	4017.1	720.1	15.2
	Control	49.3	0.00	34.4	34.2	19.8	2213.6	2523.6	53.2

Table 3. Effect of Fungicide on Stem Rust and Yield Component of Wheat

Treatment		Stem rust						
Variety	Fungicide	TRS (%)	PDC (%)	KPS	TKW (g)	GY (kgha-1)	GY (loss)	
							(kgha ⁻¹)	(%)
Ogolcho	Rex®Duo	12.6	62.7	50.3	36.7	4023.5	374.3	8.5
	Tilt 250 EC	7.1	75.6	53.7	38.3	4397.8	0.00	0.00
	Control	33.8	0.00	31.3	21.4	1917.2	2480.6	56.4

Yellow Rust Head Infection

Head infections were common during the growing season. The untreated plot had the highest head infection of 34.4%, while the application of Rex®Duo reduced it to 2.1% (Table 2). Yellow rust attacked the glumes and awns of bread wheat. This caused spores to accumulate on the surface of the developing

grain. These led to head infection and lasted until crop maturity. The control plot experienced significant yield and quality losses as a result of these factors. The current finding is consistent with the work of Dimmock and Gooding (2002), who reported significant reductions in grain yield and quality in susceptible varieties due to yellow rust. However, the use of both fungicides effectively controlled yellow rust head infection in treated plots. Furthermore, Rex®Duo is more effective in controlling head infection than Tilt 250 EC. Therefore, application of fungicides close to or just after head emergence resulted in an increase of grain yield.

Kernel per Spike

The kernel per spike differed significantly between the two locations due to the effect of wheat varieties and fungicides treatment. The longest spike (59.8) was recorded from a Rex®Duo treated plot on the Denda'a variety at Alichu, while the shortest spike (34.2) was recorded from an untreated plot in the same location (Table 2). In another location (Mareko), the maximum kernel per spike of 53.7 was obtained from Tilt 250 EC treated plot on the variety Ogolcho, whereas the lowest kernel per spike of 31.7 was obtained from untreated plot (Table 3). Fungicides application significantly increased the number of spikes while decreasing the risk of wheat rust disease infection. In spite of significant benefit of fungicides as management option, the genetic potential of the variety used determines the kernel per spike of the plant.

Thousand Kernel Weight

The thousand kernel weight (TKW) was significantly affected by fungicides treatment and wheat variety used at both locations. At Alichu the maximum value of TKW (40.3g) was obtained in the plot treated Rex®Duo from bread wheat variety Denda'a whereas, the lowest TKW (19.8g) was recorded from untreated plot on the same variety (Table 2). On the other hand, the variety Ogolcho combined with Tilt 250 EC produced the highest thousand kernel weight (36.7) at Mareko, while the same variety produced a lower thousand kernel weight (21.4) on the untreated plot (Table 3). Both test fungicides performed better in TKW than the nil (unsprayed) treatment. The findings are consistent with those of Tesfaye et al. (2018), who reported thousand kernel weight increments due to application of Rex®Duo and Tilt 250 EC against yellow rust at Guji Zone Southern Ethiopia.

Grain Yield

The results of this study clearly showed that wheat varieties and fungicides had a significant effect on grain yield at both locations (Tables 1 and 2). The minimum grain yield of (2213.6kg ha^{-1}) and (1917.2kg ha^{-1}) were obtained from untreated plots at Alichu and Mareko, respectively. At Alichu, the maximum grain yield of 4737.2kg ha^{-1} was obtained from Rex®Duo treated plots whereas, the maximum grain yield of 4023.5kg ha^{-1} were obtained from of Tilt 250 EC treated plot at Mareko. Application of both fungicides results in significant yield increment at both locations. Singh et al. (2016) also reported 44.29 % yield increment of grain yield when treated with fungicide as compared to untreated plot. Similarly, Sharma et al. (2016) found that different fungicides improved wheat yield by up to 39% when compared to an unsprayed plot. The infection of both bread wheat varieties known to be previously resistant to yellow rust and stem rust might be due to the evolution of new race or pathotypes of the pathogen. The evolution of these pathotypes results in breakdown of resistance gen in many commercial bread wheat varieties. Due to the breakdown of these resistance gen to rust continuous utilization of foliar fungicides increased several countries of the world (Murray and Brennan, 2009; Zhensheng Kang, et al., 2010). This therefore calls for an urgent need for developing varieties that are resistant to the existing aggressive pathotypes is mandatory through identification of important source of resistance gene.

Cost Benefit Analysis

There is limited information on the performance and economic benefit of fungicides by farmers in controlling wheat rust diseases. Table 4 provides cost benefit analysis of total varying costs, and net

benefits. At Alichu, the maximum net return of 1683.8\$ha⁻¹ was obtained from Rex®Duo treated plot. Whereas at Mareko, the highest net return of 1654.1\$ha⁻¹ were obtained from Tilt 250 EC treated plot from bread wheat variety Ogolcho. The result of the cost benefit analysis suggested that the application of Rex®Duo was effective in controlling the yellow rust and achieving higher economic return. In another location Mareko: The application of Tilt 250 EC result in the better economic return by controlling the stem rust disease. Therefore, both fungicides starting from the onset of the disease resulted in not only high grain yield but also high net benefit. The results of this study have close conformity with the work done by Vamshidhar *et al.* (1998) that reported the specific economic benefit of improved wheat cultivar from fungicide treatment. Similarly, Wiik and Rosenqvist (2010) showed that the use of a fungicide in winter wheat in Southern Sweden was more profitable. Before using technology innovation, farmers must understand the costs and advantages of treatments. The study assessed the treatments' financial benefits in order to generate suggestions from the agronomic data. This helps the farmers in the study area choosing the best combination of resources. The study's findings showed that applying fungicides had greater net advantages than using no spray or control treatments (Table 4). However fungicide application is not always a affordable option to control rust diseases. This is because fungicides application results in significantly increased production costs for farmers (Hodson, 2011). Therefore it is important to use resistant wheat varieties in the production system to be sustainable and economical.

Table 4. Effect of Fungicides on Net Return of Bread Wheat Varieties

Location	Treatment		FC+AC (\$ha ⁻¹)	GY (Qtha ⁻¹)	GYI (Qtha ⁻¹)	GYIP	Rn(\$ ha ⁻¹)
Alichu	Danda'a	Rex®Duo	69.45	47.4	25.3	1753.3	1683.8
		Tilt 250 EC	57.65	40.2	18.1	1254.3	1196.6
		Control	0.00	22.1	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mareko	Ogolcho	Rex®Duo	69.45	40.2	21	1455.3	1385.7
		Tilt 250 EC	57.65	43.9	24.7	1711.7	1654.1
		Control	0.00	19.2	0.00	0.00	0.00

Note: FC=Fungicide cost (\$ ha⁻¹), AC = Fungicide application, GYI=Grain yield increment from fungicide application (qt ha⁻¹), P= wheat price (\$ qt⁻¹), Rn= net return from fungicide application (\$ ha⁻¹).

Conclusion and Recommendation

A comprehensive or integrated approach is required to reduce yield loss due to rust disease. The cultivation of resistant cultivars is the first step in wheat rust management. This should be supported by identifying wheat varieties with long-lasting resistance for more effective, profitable, and sustainable rust control. The demonstration of integrated wheat rust management revealed that varieties with moderately susceptible reactions to yellow rust and stem rust diseases performed best when treated with fungicides. As a result, Rex®Duo is the best fungicide for yellow rust control, while Tilt 250 EC is better suited for stem rust. Both fungicides significantly increase crop yield by reducing both quantitative and qualitative losses. These fungicides should be applied prophylactically and repeatedly with the expectation of achieving with the expectation of a return on investment under high yielding situations.

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